

INVESTIGATION OF PRINTABLE COLOR GAMUT IN DIGITAL PRINTING ON BIODEGRADABLE FLEXIBLE PACKAGING MATERIALS

Klaudia Maňúrová¹, Edina Preklet¹, Csaba Horváth²

¹ University of Sopron, Sopron, Hungary

² University of Óbuda, Budapest, Hungary

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vach.klaudia@gmail.com

Abstract: *Digital printing is constantly winning more and more space between the printing techniques, demand of the market on short runs, personalized prints and short turnaround times is growing rapidly. In the same way is growing the demand on eco-friendlier, preferably biodegradable substrates for production of flexible packaging. In our research we aim to examine, how does biodegradable substrates effect the printable color spectrum, how the connection of compostable inks and biodegradable printing substrates effect on the printable color spectrum.*

Keywords: biodegradability, compostability, color gamut, digital printing, packaging

1 INTRODUCTION

Biodegradable materials are becoming a popular possibility for the consumers demanding more ecological and greener solutions. The biggest advantage of these polymers is, that they didn't remain stable for many years, but they are able to be broken down by microbes under stated circumstances and can be turned into biomass, water and carbon dioxide. We suppose, that biobased-materials will not solve the entire plastic crisis, but they can help to reduce the amount of plastic made from crude oil or natural gas.

Flexible packaging is a dominant part of the printing sector, because more than 70 percent of the market is accounted for food - there will always be high demand for food packaging. (Machikawa, 2021). Flexo printing will be later on

the dominant printing method for medium-to-long-run jobs, but there is a rapidly growing demand on short runs. The rise of e-commerce and social media has led the modern consumer to expect a wide range of consumer packaged goods and fast delivery. (Machikawa, 2021) Therefore the product lifecycles are much shorter, we can observe a big pressure to handle the short run jobs, also a quick turnaround is expected. Flexible packaging printers must change their policies to meet these needs. This is the point, where digital printing steps in. According to the newest trends and forecasts, flexoprinting will stay the dominant printing technique when printing on flexible packaging materials but digital printing is forecasted to make the most dynamic growth in the printing industry.

For the purposes of our project, we used two types of biodegradable materials – PLA and PP. Biodegradable polypropylene is a thermoplastic polymer, with good strength, stiffness and resistance capabilities. The material is durable for a long period, but thanks to an additive, the products from this material can be decomposed in a landfill. The PLA foil – polylactide, polylactic acid – is a biodegradable thermoplastic polyester, which is made from renewable raw materials and is industrially compostable. Our general focus is the printability of flexible packaging materials by the modern and broadly used printing techniques.

Every digital printing process is unique and it's similarly complicated to have color management under control as in analogue printing techniques. The final result is significantly depending on the printed substrate. The digital print on flexible packaging materials needs to be researched, therefore our testframe will include testcharts to be able to assess the printable color space and various other test elements to evaluate the possibilities. The testframes were be printed on PLA and biodegradable polypropylene films. Through this research we plan to broaden the disposable information about the digital printing technology in connection to circular economy and greener packaging. The evaluation also contains visualizations of the printable color spectrum and other possible descriptions of the printing process on these biodegradable materials.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Polylactic acid and polypropylene

Some new aspects of the packaging, like the longer shelf life, international safety and quality standards, etc. have won on importance in the last years. Moreover, the concern about the environmental consequences of the

extensive use of nonbiodegradable plastic materials for packaging has boosted the demand for bio-based sustainable packaging solutions. (Sharma, 2021) For the aims of this research we used two popular biodegradable materials – PLA and biodegradable polypropylene.

The usage of biodegradable materials in flexible packaging is continuously conquering place. There are several bioplastics, but not all of them are suitable for flexible packaging use. Polylactic acid is a very popular, feasible replacement of petroleum-derived packaging materials. Being fully biodegradable and being derived from natural resources, PLA appears to be a beneficial choice in the packaging sector. (Sharma, 2021). Polylactic acid (PLA) is an aliphatic polyester made up of lactic acid building blocks and a biodegradable material that can be processed using the common processing techniques, such as injection molding, extrusion, and blow molding. (Goodsel and Madbouly, 2021). It can be produced from natural renewable plant sources like corn sugar, sugar cane or potato. Because PLA is compostable and derived from renewable sources, it has been considered as one of the solutions to alleviate solid waste disposal problems and to lessen the dependence on petroleum-based plastics for packaging materials. (Lim, Auras and Rubino, 2008). There can still appear some problems with the quality of the PLA, like brittleness, weak thermal, barrier or mechanical properties, but there is a really intensive research on the modification of the material-structure by adding some nanoparticles like nanoclays, nanopigments or carbon nanotubes (D'Anna, Arrigo and Frache, 2021). To defeat these problems is possible to blend the PLA with other bio-polymers. Blending is a more practical and cost-effective method for this purpose.

Polypropylene is usually not a biodegradable material. The strong polymers creating the polypropylene are steady, allowing the material to be durable over long periods of time and to extend the shelf life of its product many times over. The degradation time of standard polypropylene – and plastic foils at all – is between 200 and 1000 years, what can't be held for an ecofriendly solution, mainly for the one way packaging applications. As well as there are many researches to improve the bioplastics, there can be observed many good results in making the polyolefins biodegradable. Adding some special additives or nanocomposites seem to solve this problem. Thus, new blends are coming to the market, for example chitosan/ZnO nanocomposite (Darwish et al., 2021), modified-cobalt stearate (Sable, Ahuja and Bhunia, 2020) or other specific additives are mixed to the polypropylene. The effect is the biodegradability of the polypropylene, however the rates of the biodegradation will be various in the biologically-active landfills according the product configuration, the solid content, temperature and moisture levels of

the landfill. For the aims of this research we selected these two materials – the PLA and the degradable PP - to examine their printability attributes. We've got a third printed sample printed on standard polyester PET foil (biaxially-oriented polyethylene terephthalate is a polyester film made from stretched polyethylene terephthalate and it's widely spread because of its high tensile strength, barrier properties, stability, transparency, reflectivity, etc.), so we could make also a comparison to a widely used, but not biodegradable material.

2. 2 Printing machine, inks and the frame

Hewlett–Packard Indigo Division develops and produces several types of digital printing presses. As mentioned previously, the scope of our research was to investigate the printable color gamut by digital printing, where for the purposes of our project the testing machine is the by now one-and-only HP Indigo 20000 in Hungary. The ink used in the HP Indigo 20000 – the ElectroInk - is a complex fluid of unique rheological and electrical properties. It is a mixture of a dielectric fluid carrier, polymeric particles bearing colorants and additives (Forgacs and Teishev, 2013). Due to some additives the polymeric particles got an electrical charge and are managed by an external electrical field. During the process the ink is transferred from roller to roller and its concentration increases from dilute dispersion in the ink reservoir to completely dry on the substrate ensuring that each printed frame is different (Forgacs and Teishev, 2013).

HP digital printing technology is a perspective solution for eco-friendly customers, because HP Indigo already offers impressive ecological attributes. Thus, they achieved the certification by TUV Austria, getting the marks of compostability to HP, verifying HP Indigo ElectroInks, so they can be used as printing inks for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation in accordance with leading standards, such as EU regulation EN 13432. (Packaging Europe, 2019). It's also an impressive fact, that HP Indigo is a member of the European consortium called Circular Economy for Flexible Packaging. Thus the connection of a biodegradable substrate and compostable inks can result an ecological solution in the flexible packaging industry.

The biggest possible frame size was 1120x740 mm. It is an impressive size, where it was possible to put really any test element, we wanted. For further researches we implemented all elements of a flexographic printing testchart, because we plan to realize some comparative investigations. On our digital testframe can be found smooth gradients, tone scales, fields for the grey balance, the positive and negative text and line elements, the testchart for the

profile measuring and a lot of pictures or the visual control. The testframe is shown on the Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Testframe used for the digital printed sample

3 RESULTS

For the purposes of this publication we focus only on the printable color gamut based on these specific printed samples.

3.1 Measuring and evaluation

The best way for the characterization of the printable color gamut was to measure and generate ICC profiles from each sample. The ICC profile is a set of data that characterizes a color input or output device, or a color space, according to standards promulgated by the International Color Consortium (ICC). Profiles describe the color attributes of a particular device or viewing requirement by defining a mapping between the device source or target color space and a profile connection space (PCS). (International Color Consortium, 2021). For our measuring we used the X-Rite i1iO Automated Scanning Table, what's a hands-free test chart reading device for automated color profiling on a variety of substrates with reduced risk of color measurement errors. The related program to handle the measurements is the

i1 Profiler. The samples were measured and the ICC profiles generated. On the next figures we show the 3D visualizations of the ICC profiles of PLA and PP.

Figure 2: ICC profile visualizations for polypropylene under different angles

Figure 3: ICC profile visualizations for polylactic acid under different angles

As it can be seen, the profile of polypropylene is smooth and regular, no discrepancies can be seen in the profile measured from the testchart, containing 1472 patches. In the case of the PLA we can see, that some either there are some print issues or for the PLA we should calculate with other printability specifications indeed. After getting the first results, two additional control measurements were made and the result was exactly the same. As it can be seen on the figures, the ICC profile of the PLA is a little bit narrower and with several color issues are appearing.

3. 2 Comparison of the ICC-profiles

The International Standards Organization has defined in ISO 12647 a set of Graphic Arts standards for printing, but the digital printing for flexible packaging isn't included yet. As mentioned before, our wider research stretches out to flexo printing too, where it is not possible to define and standardize a specific color space, in flexo, the ISO standards only give the recommended hue angle for those colors, and it's up to the printer to establish the best $L^*a^*b^*$ targets for a given substrate. (Harig, 2015). Offset print has his given standards, but different parts of the world interpret these standards in their own way. In North America IDEAlliance's GRACoL and in Europe FOGRA39 are the specifications for offset printing that conform to ISO 12647-2 for a

number one grade, coated paper. (Harig, 2015) For the purposes of this research we needed a universal profile, to show the differences between the substrates. We have chosen the European FOGRA39 – however it could be almost any of general profiles. We made two types of comparisons, we compare PLA and PP to FOGRA39 and PLA and PP to PET ICC profile. The results are as shown below on the figures.

Figure 4: ICC profile color space comparison for polypropylene under different angles

On the figures we show the extensions of the printable color spaces. The colored space shows FOGRA and the grey grid stands for the PP ICC profile. We can see, that the light green, yellow, red and blue tones are slightly wider printable on PP as they are defined in FOGRA. The printable color space is narrower in the darker tones, where the L^* values are lower, that's visible on the figure in the right.

Figure 5: ICC profile color space comparison for polylactic acid under different angles

The polylactic acid feels as harder and more fragile than PP. Nonetheless the printable color spectrum is wider than in the cas of the polypropylene. On the figures above is visible, that almost through the whole spectrum of the FOGRA39 the PLA ICC profile exceeds the values. A narrower spectrum is visible only in darker reddish and greenish parts.

The second task of our comparative research we set out was to compare the two biodegradable foils to polyester PET. The results are as shown below.

Figure 6: ICC profile color space comparison between polyester PET and polypropylene under different angles

According to our previous experiences from flexoprinting, PET and PP should have quite similar printability properties. This has been confirmed during this examination too, because the printable colour spaces are almost the same. This indicates also the fact, that the additives, they make polypropylene under defined circumstances biodegradable, does not affect the printability properties. The comparison is shown on the figure 6. The next figures visualize the color spaces of PET vs. PLA.

Figure 7: ICC profile color space comparison between polyester PET and polylactic acid under different angles

Similarly as in the case of FOGRA39 vs. PLA the results are better for the polylactic acid. The printable color spectrum of PLA exceeds almost in every point the polyester PET, there are just a few locations, where PLA does not reach the PET values.

In our research we got confirmation of the competitiveness of the biodegradable foils with the presently widely used flexible foils. We do not have to give up the expectations of vibrant colors and impressive design because we want to produce an eco-friendly flexible packaging. The biodegradable foils printed with compostable inks can show the way, how to make flexible packaging friendly to the planet Earth.

4 CONCLUSION

During our theoretical research we haven't found studies dealing with the printable color gamut on biodegradable materials by digital printing. However, the examined foils have good reviews on printability, we wanted to know more exactly if and how the biodegradability effects on the width of the printable color spectrum. On the testframe there were printed many different elements, but its examination will be the scope of further investigations for a broader research in the field of circular packaging and printing techniques.

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